

CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS CORRELATES THE PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS IN MATHEMATICS AMONG GRADE VI PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

Mathematics education aims to inspire elementary students to solve a worded problem by using precise and specific thought. To achieve this goal, students must have the opportunity to develop their problem-solving skills by examining information and ideas written on it. Educators must emphasize students' critical thinking skills. To support this, this study aimed to determine if the critical thinking skills correlate with the problem-solving skills in Mathematics of Grade VI pupils. The respondents of this study were 70 Grade VI pupils of Malabanban Norte Elementary School and this study utilized the descriptive correlational design of research. As revealed by the findings, the student's critical thinking skills in all of the variables are at a high level. Meanwhile, the result of the scores of the students in determining the level of the problem-solving skills on snapshots, accuracy, and representation and communication were at the proficient level and on the concepts and application and strategies and approaches were at the advanced level. This implies that most of the students were able to understand the worded problem because they were able to provide solutions and correct answers based on their scores. The results also showed an exists significant relationship between the critical thinking and problem-solving skills of the student-respondents specifically obtained from the sub-variable organization in interpretation, analysis, and reasoning to all the sub-variables of problem-solving skills. This indicates that when solving a worded problem, students are utilizing their critical thinking skills such as organizing ideas before applying a specific solution and obtaining the correct answer. The study suggests that efforts need to be undertaken by teachers to stimulate the critical thinking and problem-solving skills of the students toward improved academic performance in Mathematics.

Keywords: Critical Thinking Skills and Problem-Solving Skills